

Can Toll-Like Receptor 4 Gene Polymorphism Play A Role in Pathogenesis of Breast Cancer?

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Abstract

Introduction: Breast cancer is one of the most common causes of death from cancer in women worldwide. Dynamic interaction between tumors and the immune system is essential for tumor survival, growth, and metastasis. The immune system is known to play a major role in preventing tumor progression by recognizing tumor antigens. Recent studies have shown that dysregulation of innate immunity receptors such as Toll-like receptors (TLRs) play an important role in the activation of natural and adaptive immunity in response to endogenous hazard signals from pathogens and damaged or dead cells. TLRs are expressed in the immune system cells and some epithelial cells. Recent studies have shown that these receptors are also exaggerated in malignant breast cancer cells. Many studies have shown that TLR4 gene expression is increased in breast cancer cells, but also associated with metastasis. However, there is no study that could correlate TLR4 gene polymorphisms with breast cancer.

Materials and methods: We conducted a case study

with 100 patients and 100 healthy subjects and planned to investigate whether there is a relationship between TLR4 gene polymorphisms [rs4986790 (Asp299Gly) ve rs4986791 (Thr399Ile)] and breast cancer. In this study, polymerase chain reaction (PCR) based restriction fragment length polymorphism (RFLP) method was used for gene polymorphisms.

Results: It was observed that there was relationship between breast cancer and TLR4 gene polymorphisms. Because TLR-4 plays an active role in the innate immune system, the loss of function of this protein may lead to a depressed immune response, thus promoting cancer development.

Introduction

Breast cancer is the most common cause of cancer-related deaths in females, and represents a major worldwide health issue [1]. Toll-like receptors (TLRs) are generally expressed by immune cells such as macrophages, dendritic cells, mast cells and eosinophils, as well as some epithelial cells [2]. TLRs take part a central role in the recognition of deleterious

molecules from invading microorganisms or internal tissue damage, activating specific transcriptional responses including the Nuclear Factor Kappa B (NF- κ B), Mitogen-Activated Protein Kinase (MAPK) and interferon regulatory factor pathways, which result in inflammation [3].

TLR4 was the first TLR to be detected in humans, and is one of the most remarkable members of the TLR family, expressed by both immune and non-immune cells [4]. Up regulation of TLR4 is definitely associated with the increased existence of metastasis in patients with breast cancer [5]. Dynamic arrangement of TLR signaling is necessary for the suppression of chronic inflammation and tissue damage. A number of mechanisms have been noticed to negatively regulate TLR responses, including cell membrane-bound TLR suppressors and soluble TLRs (sTLRs) [6]. One of the significant negative regulators of TLR-signaling is the formation of extracellular sTLRs, which work as decoy receptors to hinder ligand-induced signaling [7]. Many research groups have revealed that TLRs are expressed on both host immune and tumor cells, where they influence the immune response, uncontrolled tumor proliferation, resistance to apoptosis, metastasis and tumor cell escape from immune surveillance [8]. A number of anxieties about the effect of the endogenous negative regulation of TLR signaling on host immune and tumor cells stay unresolved. In this context, the aim of the present study was to assess TLR4 gene polymorphisms and to explore their relationship with the clinicopathological factors of patients with breast cancer.

Subjects and Methods

Subjects

A total of 200 female subjects were included into the present study, and were classified into the following groups: Group I, 100 healthy control subjects with no history of breast cancer; Group II, 50 subjects recently diagnosed with non-metastatic breast cancer; and Group III, 50 subjects with metastatic breast cancer. All patients were recruited from the Bulent Ecevit

University Hospital Oncology Center (Zonguldak, Turkey) between August 2014 and May 2016. Demographics data were provided from all participants and included age, menopausal status, number of children, lactation history, marital status and family history of breast cancer. The present study was approved by the ethics committee of Bulent Ecevit University Hospital and informed consent was obtained from each participant.

Exclusion criteria

Patients with autoimmune diseases, other types of malignancy, liver and kidney diseases were excluded from the present study.

Sample collection

A 5-ml sample of whole blood was collected from each subject after an overnight fast. The blood samples were allowed to clot for 15 min at room temperature and then centrifuged for 10 min at 12,000 x g (14.810 g). The separated serum was stored at -80°C for the assessment of TLR-4 gene polymorphisms by Polymerase Chain Reaction (PCR).

Method

In this study, Polymerase Chain Reaction (PCR) based Restriction Fragment Length Polymorphism (RFLP) method was used for detecting gene polymorphisms. As far as TLR4 gene polymorphisms are concerned, PCR was performed with 50-CTGCTCTAGAGGGCC TGTG-30 as forward and 50 - TTCAATAGTCACACTCAC CAG-30 as reverse primer for Asp299Gly (rs4986790), resulting in a 140bp fragment. After denaturation at 95°C, 38 cycles of DNA amplification were performed using Taq DNA Polymerase 2 x Master Mix RED (Ampliqon Biomol, Hamburg, Germany) at 95 °C for 30 s, 61 °C for 30 s and 72 °C for 30 s. Digestion with BccI at 37 °C (New England Biolabs Inc., Ipswich, MA, USA) results in two fragments of 77bp and 63bp for the G-allele and one fragment of 140bp (no digestion) for the allele which are visualized on a 2.5% agarose gel. For TLR4 Thr399Ile (rs4986791) polymorphism analysis, PCR was performed with 50-CTACCAAGCCTTGAGTTTCTAG- 30 as forward

and 50-AAGCTCAGATCTAAATACCT-30 as reverse primer. The resulting 110bp PCR products were digested using the restriction enzyme BslI at 55°C and analyzed on a 2.5% agarose gel. The unrestricted products (110 bp) represent the TT genotype while the completely restricted products (89 and 21 bp) represent the CC genotype.

Statistical analysis

The data were analyzed using the SPSS software package version 20.0 (IBM Corp). Qualitative data are presented as counts and percentages. Comparisons between the categorical variables of different groups were assessed using the χ^2 test. Normally distributed quantitative data are presented as the mean±standard deviation, while non-normally distributed data are expressed as the median, minimum and maximum values. For normally distributed data, comparisons between ≥ 2 groups were conducted using the F-test (one-way ANOVA) Duncan method. For correlation analysis, the Pearson's correlation coefficient (r) was calculated. Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curve statistics were applied to determine assay sensitivity and specificity. In order to determine the

diagnostic accuracy of the combination of biomarkers, logistic regression analysis was used to estimate the predicted probabilities, which were subsequently used to generate a ROC curve. The method described by DeLong was used for comparing the area under the ROC curves (AUCs). $P \leq 0.05$ was considered to indicate a statistically significant difference, and significance test results are quoted as two-tailed probabilities.

Results

Demographical data

Patients in both the metastatic and non-metastatic breast cancer groups were significantly older than those in the control group ($P=0.013$ and $P=0.002$, respectively; **Table 1**). A family history of breast cancer was also significantly more likely in patients with non-metastatic breast cancer than in healthy controls ($P=0.025$; Table I). No significant differences were detected between patients with breast cancer and the controls with respect to lactation history and number of children (**Table 1**).

Table 1: Demographic features of patients with breast cancer and healthy control group.

Characteristics	Group I (control)	Group II (non-metastatic)	Group III (metastatic)	X ² test	P-value	P1	P2	P3
Age, years				12.25	0.013	0.01	0.00	0.28
Range	28-66	30-69	32-71			3	2	2
Mean±SD	46.0±11.05	50.9±10.62	52.0±8.67					
Family history, n (%)				5.21	0.026	0.02	0.31	0.07
Negative	78(78.0)	46(92.0)	41(82.0)			5	1	
Positive	22(22.0)	4(8.0)	9(18.0)					
Lactation history, n (%)				2.32	0.125	0.36	0.11	0.18
No	16(16.0)	5(10.0)	4(8.0)			5	1	9
Yes	84(84.0)	45(90.0)	46(92.0)					

No of children, n (%)				1.65	0.366	0.29 6	0.21 6	0.40 9
01-Mar	44(44.0)	19(38.0)	22(44.0)					
04-May	36(36.0)	22(44.0)	22(44.0)					
6+	20(20.0)	4(8.0)	6(12.0)					

P<0.05. P1, comparison between the control and non-metastatic group; P2, comparison between the control and metastatic groups; P3, comparison between the metastatic and non-metastatic groups.

A significant increase in the number of grade III patients was detected among those with metastatic, compared with those with non-metastatic breast cancer (P=0.0001; **Table 2**). Patients with non-metastatic breast cancer showed a significant increase in tumor size and regional lymph node involvement compared with the metastatic patients (P=0.001). Moreover, a significant increase in distant metastasis was also observed in the metastatic, compared with the non-

metastatic patients (P=0.0001; **Table 2**). The patients with metastatic breast cancer also exhibited a significant increase in Human Epidermal Growth factor 2 receptor (HER2) expression compared with the non-metastatic patients P=0.0433). However, a significant increase in progesterone receptor (PR) expression was detected in the non-metastatic, compared with the metastatic patients (P=0.033; **Table 2**).

Table 2: Clinical characteristics of patients with breast cancer.

Patient characteristics	Group II (non-metastatic)		Group III (metastatic)		X ² test	P-value
	No.	%	No.	%		
Menopausal status					2.36	0.214
Premenopausal	21	42	24	48		
Postmenopausal	29	58	26	52		
Pathology					2.08	0.106
Infiltrating ductal carcinoma	44	88	48	96		
Infiltrating lobular carcinoma	6	12	2	4		
HER2					4.083	0.043
Pozitif	30	60	37	74		
Negatif	20	40	13	26		
ER					0.0001	0.999
Pozitif	10	20	10	20		
Negatif	40	80	40	80		
PR					4.504	0.033
Pozitif	16	32	9	18		
Negatif	34	68	41	82		
Lympho vascular invasion					13.2	0.001
Pozitif	12	24	13	26		

Negatif	38	76	27	54		
Tstage					173.1	0.001
I	2	4	20	40		
II	27	54	24	48		
III	19	38	5	10		
IV	2	4	1	2		
N stage					297.5	0.001
0	1	2	18	36		
1	11	22	9	18		
2	24	48	19	38		
3	14	28	4	8		
M stage					25.6	0.0001
Positive	0	0	50	100		
Negative	50	100	0	0		
Grade					36.2	0.0001
I	38	76	3	6		
II	11	22	44	88		
III	1	2	3	6		
Presentation					504.4	0.001
Breast lump	38	76	0	0		
Nipple retraction	4	8	47	94		
Nipple discharge	6	12	1	2		
Nipple and areola ulcer	1	2	1	2		
Swollen inflamed breast	1	2	1	2		

P<0.05. T, tumor size; ER, estrogen receptor; PR, progesterone receptor; Her2, human epidermal growth factor receptor 2; N, lymph node status; M, metastatic status.

A significant increase in the number of breast lumps was detected in non-metastatic breast cancer compared with metastatic patients. On the other hand, a significant increase in nipple retraction was observed in the metastatic patients compared with the non-metastatic patients (P=0.001; [Table 2](#)). No significant differences in estrogen receptor (ER) expression, menopausal status and pathology were detected

between patients with metastatic and non-metastatic breast cancer ([Table 2](#)).

TLR4 gene polymorphisms

In this study it was found a statistically significant correlation between TLR-4 gene polymorphisms and breast cancer ([Table 3 and 4](#)).

Table 3: Frequency of genotype of TLR4 Asp 299 Glyve TLR4 Thr399Ile polymorphisms.

SNP	Genotype	Controls n=102 (%)	SSPE Patients n=100(%)	P Value	OR (95 % CI)
TLR4	AA	99 (97,1)	95 (95,0)		Reference

Asp299Gly	AG	3 (2,9)	4 (4,0)	0,451	1.389 (0.303-6.373)
	GG	0 (0)	1 (1,0)		1683000000*
TLR4 Thr399Ile	CC	99 (98,0)	94 (94,0)		Reference
	CT	2 (2,0)	5 (5,0)	0.242	2.633 (0.499-13.902)
	TT	0 (0)	5 (5,0)	1 (1,0)	1701000000*

Table 4: Frequency of alleles of TLR4 Asp 299 Glyve TLR4 Thr399Ile polymorphisms.

SNP	Allele	Controls n=102 (%)	SSPE Patients n=100 (%)	p Value	OR (95 % CI)
TLR4 Asp299Gly	A	201 (98.5)	194 (97.0)		Reference
	G	3 (1.5)	6 (3.0)	0.334	2.077 (0.511-8.402)
TLR4 Thr399Ile	C	200 (99.0)	193 (96.5)		Reference
	T	2 (1.0)	7 (3.5)	0.104	3.627 (0.744-17.677)

Discussion

A variety of studies put forward that TLRs occur in many human tumors such as lung cancer, prostate cancer and breast cancer [9-11]. It is known that the expression of these receptors and their signaling pathways are functionally associated with tumor growth, progression and invasion. A recent study assessing the TLR2 expression in breast cancer cells demonstrated that this molecule is a critical receptor responsible for NF-kB signaling activity and highly invasive capacity of breast cancer cells [12]. In addition, the authors of two other studies reported that the expression of TLR3, TLR4 and TLR9 correlated with breast cancer aggressiveness suggesting that these receptors could be a therapeutic target in these tumors and that demoshiling of TLR4 could actively inhibit proliferation and survival of breast cancer cells [13,14]. Furthermore, breast cancer patients with a loss-of-function mutation of theTLR4 receptor have been associated with decreased disease-free survival,

verifying the major role of the immune system in the response to cytotoxic agents [15]. A substantial number of studies to date have focused on the impact of these receptors on tumors' aggressiveness, none the less only one has been conceived to screen for genetic polymorphisms with the aim of exposing the potential predictive role of TLRs in predisposition to cancer [16]. In the current study we focused on two polymorphisms in the TLR4 encoding gene (Asp299 Gly and Thr399Ile) which have been correlated with increased risk for cancer development in certain organs. We aimed to identify a possible relationship between any of these genotypes and alleles and the risk for breast cancer. We also evaluated the correlation between these polymorphisms and known clinicopathological characteristics. Concerning the Asp299 Gly and Thr399Ile polymorphisms in TLR4 encoding gene, we demonstrated a positive association between the presence of the Gly allele and the risk for breast cancer development. As presented above, TLR4

signaling in cancer cells is associated with increased formation of soluble immune mediators like IL10 that provides a protection from immune system [17]. Increased TLR4 signaling in cancer cells is also associated with increased cancer cell proliferation, resistance to apoptosis and increased invasion and metastasis by regulating metalloproteases and integrins [18,19]. On the other hand, increased expression of this receptor in immune cells is related to more efficient tumor shrinkage because of better immune response [20]. Curiously, recent studies suggest that the expression of TLR4 in Mononuclear Inflammatory Cells (MIC's) seems to increase the incidence of metastasis favoring the important role of tumor stromal cells in tumor behavior. The stromal cells participating in a chronic inflammatory procedure are esteemed to produce a variety of extracellular matrix proteins, growth factors and proteases which may act as transducers for tumor progression [21,22]. Asp299 Gly and Thr399Ile polymorphisms are believed to change the function of TLR4 in all these pathways playing an important role in the development of the neoplastic phenotype [23]. Notably, it has been reported that patients with breast cancer who have at least one TLR4 loss- of-function allele, relapse more rapidly after radiotherapy and chemotherapy than those having two wild typeTLR4 alleles. This attitude may be attributed to the truth that TLR4Asp299Gly polymorphism influences the linking of TLR4 to HMGB1, which is delivered from tumor cells damaged by cytotoxic anticancer agents [24].

The majority of recent studies demonstrate the relationship with the presence of polymorphisms in TLRs encoding genes to increased aggressiveness of breast cancer [25]. In our study however, we did not find any association between the evaluated polymorphisms and tumors' clinicopathological features. This is in consistence with other studies which dedicated the TLR4 expression in head and neck squamous cell carcinomas, which reinforced the importance of TLR4 299Gly and 399Ile alleles as markers for prognosis but did not administrate to

correlate the expression of TLR4 to tumors' clinicopathological characteristics [23]. Although increasing the number of cases at both the patients and the control group would have a positive impact on the power of the study, the current study's results might be well considered as enough strong evidence that the Gly allele at 299 of TLR4 gene yields a higher risk for breast cancer.

Conclusions

Our results indicate that Asp299Gly and Thr399Ile of TLR4 gene polymorphisms may yield an increased predisposition to breast cancer development. No correlation though was identified with the clinicopathological characteristics. Though, this is a primary study opening the way for a potentially more detailed investigation of TLRs gene polymorphisms in larger scale multiethnic patients' sample, in an endeavor to certainly clarify and exactly explain their possible role in risk increment and possible impact on treatment strategies.

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